

Communication & Dissemination Plan

Jessica Johnson - nucleareurope

13 January 2023

WP6 – D6.1 & D6.2

D6.1: Communications & Dissemination Plan			
D6.2: Communications Toolkit			
WP6	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
Prepared	Jessica Johnson	Nucleareurope (FORATOM)	
Checked			
Approved			

Table of Contents

Contents

Introduction	3
Partner contributions.....	3
Relevant Stakeholders	4
Messaging	4
Outreach	5
Conclusion.....	5

Introduction

The goal of the NPHyCo project is to assess the potential for developing large scale, low-carbon, hydrogen production facilities linked to nuclear power plants. This includes identifying potential locations where a demonstration project could eventually be built.

Interaction with relevant stakeholders plays an essential part in the development of projects. This includes informing them about the project and its outcomes, as well as providing them with the possibility of engaging with the partners and discussing and thoughts and feedback which they may have.

As part of the communication and dissemination strategy the following aspects need to be taken into account:

- To transfer knowledge and innovation gathered to different stakeholders and to receive their feedback
- To investigate if and how public awareness/acceptance about nuclear power is impacted, when linked to H2 generation
- To identify education and training needs, including using this project to encourage more young people to join the sector
- To connect / network to related other sectors or industries
- To market / advertise pilot projects in the next phase

The NPHyCo project will run over a period of 2 and a half years. In order to ensure that the communication strategy is aligned with the outcomes of the project, and that the communication needs of the different stakeholders are met, this plan is to be seen as a flexible tool which will be amended on a regular basis to ensure the best possible outcome of communication actions.

Partner contributions

Nucleareurope leads the communication and dissemination activities for the NPHyCo project. At the same time, tools, articles and recommendations will be provided to the Project Partners in order to enable them to raise awareness about the project amongst their networks. This will help ensure a broader outreach to relevant stakeholders and greater visibility for the project.

One action which all partners are strongly encouraged to implement is to include information about the NPHyCo project via their respective websites. See for example the following [webpage \(www.nphyco.org\)](http://www.nphyco.org), which can be directly copy pasted onto your websites).

Partners are also encouraged to promote the project via their relevant networks. At the same time, we draw attention to Article 15.1 of the consortium agreement which states: *The BENEFICIARIES shall not issue any **press release or similar publicity** about the PROJECT without the **prior approval of the EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE**, which shall not be unreasonably withheld or delayed longer than four weeks after receipt by the EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE. Notwithstanding the foregoing, the BENEFICIARIES may provide general information that they are participating in the PROJECT without prior approval.*

In a nutshell, this means that more official forms of communication (eg press release, publication of an article in a scientific journal/other media) require consortium approval. For general information about the project (eg a webpage on the partner's website, summary article in their own newsletter, or general information distributed via their social media channels) such approval is not required.

Relevant Stakeholders

Below is a short overview of some of the stakeholders for whom this project is of relevance:

- Industry, as they can benefit from becoming involved in the project
- Downstream users, ie those who will benefit from the hydrogen produced
- Policymakers, as having the right policy framework in place can encourage uptake of future projects
- Finance/investors, as demonstrating the economic benefits of such a project to these stakeholders can help leverage the capital needed to build future electrolyzers
- Citizens, as their acceptance of such a project will prove crucial in terms of enabling future deployment of this technology in local communities.

An initial assessment of specific stakeholders to whom the project is relevant can be found below.

Nuclear power plant operators	H2 production EPCs (engineering, procurement and construction)
Investors	Safety authorities
Notified bodies	Hydrogen consumers (eg industry)
Policymakers	Local community (ie those in locations being considered for the pilot project)
Education & Training institutions	Media

ACTION: A dedicated metaplan session to be organised in 2023 in order to map all stakeholders to whom this project is of relevance (information about what a Metaplan Session entails can be found [here](#)).

Messaging

Many of the messages to be communicated about the project will be developed as the results of the different Work Packages become available. Nevertheless, below is a simple overview of some key messages which can form the basis of the general outreach, at least at the start of the project.

Work on more specific, targeted messaging, depending on the deliverable and the stakeholder to whom it is of most relevance, will be developed as the project evolves and outcomes become available.

Ultimate goal of the project		
Identify the potential for building a large-scale hydrogen facility linked to a nuclear power plant		
Top message (elevator pitch)		
Nuclear has the potential to produce vast quantities of low-carbon hydrogen which is key to decarbonising Europe's economy in a sustainable way		
Initial outreach proposal		
<i>Stakeholder</i>	<i>Message</i>	<i>Tool</i>
Nuclear power plant operators	Added value to NPP of linking to a hydrogen production facility	Webinars/Newsletters/presentations at relevant events + meetings
H2 production EPCs	Benefits of using nuclear to power an electrolyser + existing nuclear services and equipment which can be used at both sites	One-to-one meetings with suppliers in Member States where pilot project is being considered

Hydrogen consumers (eg industry)	Such a project can enable a stable and constant supply of low-carbon hydrogen at an affordable cost	Dedicated Webinars (at EU level at national level in Member States where pilot project is being considered)
Investors	Long-term benefits of investing in such projects (return on investment)	Dedicated Webinars
Education & Training institutions	Overview of skills required for the workforce	Outreach to ENEN for information transfer

ACTION: A dedicated metaplan session to be organised on a yearly basis in order to identify and refine key messages towards stakeholders based on project outcomes.

Outreach

In order to ensure a maximum outreach of the project and its results, Partners are encouraged to promote the work as widely as possible. Below are some suggestions as to how this can be achieved:

- Page dedicated to the project on partner websites (see above)
- Promotion of the project via social media (a dedicated LinkedIn page will be created + propose to use following hashtags: #NPHyCo & #nuclearhydrogen)
- Inclusion of project articles in newsletters
- Presentation of the project at relevant meetings (ie to inform relevant stakeholders of general goal of project, provide updates etc)
- Identify key events of relevance to the project and aim to obtain speaker slots
- Identify key publications (eg scientific journals) with the goal of publishing articles highlighting the results of the project

The following dedicated outreach activities will be organised under Task 6.2:

- 3 webinars (As of Q2/3 2023). These webinars will focus on key stakeholders (identified as project results become available) and will enable communication about status of the project. Where feasible, webinars should be topics focused and the goal is to ensure the involvement of all stakeholders to whom that topic is of relevant in the webinar. Generally speaking, as an online event, these should be more about presenting the topic, with feedback sessions falling under the workshops (see below).
- 3 Workshops (During 2 half of the project). The goal of these workshops is not just to present project results, but to also obtain feedback from stakeholders which will then be considered by project partners. These workshops will primarily occur at national level in Member States where pilot project is being considered. As with the webinars, these should be topics focused and the goal is to ensure the involvement of all stakeholders to whom that topic is of relevant in the workshop.
- 2 events at EU level (one halfway through the project and one at the end). These events will bring together key EU representatives of the different stakeholder groups identified.

Conclusion

In order to ensure a timely communication of the project, it is important to maintain a close interaction with the different WPs to have a clear overview of results which are expected and when. Furthermore,

partners are encouraged to keep the WP6 leader informed of any communications actions in order to ensure a trace of all activities for reporting purposes.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Atomic Energy Community ('EC-Euratom'). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.